

ISic1056

I.Sicily inscription 1056

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry of the Intagliatella

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140536

1. ἐνθάδε κῆ-
2. τε Εὐτύχης
3. ζήσας ας ἀμέ-
4. πτως ²⁶ἀμέμπτως²⁶ ἔτη
5. κς. χωρὶ δ' ἰ [ς]
6. χώραν δικέ-
7. ων ²⁶δικαίων²⁶ τῆ [πρὸ] α' εἶδ (ῶν)
8. [Ἰαν]ου#⁷αρίων. ²⁶Ἰανουαρίων²⁶.
- 9.

Edition: PHI175471

1. ἐνθάδε κῆ-
2. τε Εὐτύχης
3. ζήσας ας ἀμέ-
4. πτως ²⁶ἀμέμπτως²⁶ ἔτη
5. κε. χώρι δ' ἰ [ς]
6. χώραν δικέ-
7. ων ²⁶δικαίων²⁶ τῆ (πρὸ) α' Εἶδ (ῶν)

8. [Iav]ουαρίων.

9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492684

EDCS 39102211

PHI 140536

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Bibliography

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